

Simulation Analysis of a Wideband Antenna on a Drone

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Abstract— Wireless systems have been upgraded over the past several years and as a result, drone-based communications have found a wide range of applications. This paper presents the performance of a printed log-periodic antenna, which operates in the frequency range from 0.7 to 6.5 GHz when mounted on the top of a drone. The effect of a metallic mast and a base plate is considered in our analysis. From our simulations, it is observed that an improvement in realized gain of 1.6 dB is obtained over a frequency band of 2 to 6.5 GHz. All simulations are performed using CST Studio Suite.

Keywords— *CST Studio Suite, Finite Integration Technique, Half-Power Beamwidth, Printed Log-periodic antenna, Quadcopter, Realized Gain.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The quadcopter market has recently gained a lot of prominence and has found a range of applications in domestic as well as in commercial areas [1]. Drones can carry out various high-frequency measurements [2] including far-field, near-field measurements, mobile network testing, interference hunting, direction finding, imaging, etc. [3]. In a recent study, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) have been employed to conduct measurements and characterize the radiation patterns of low-frequency antennas in the presence of interfering sources [4]. It is evident that all these applications require GPS, flight control modules, directional antennas [5], and beamforming capabilities [6], to steer the beam in the desired direction. This type of beamforming will decrease the side-lobe levels to less than -20 dB and provide additional nulls to effectively suppress the interference signals.

Modern drones are equipped with an array of devices that aid in autonomous navigation, establish connections with ground control stations, and employ various sensors. This will contribute to the creation of substantial electromagnetic interference. Therefore, the installation of an antenna considering the limited space available on a drone will require a systematic analysis. The electromagnetic (EM) coupling and

space constraints point to an architectural integration into a UAV, that can accommodate annular slot antennas [7] with Voltage Standing Wave Ratio (VSWR) < 2.0 within a range of 2.3 to 2.5 GHz, waveguides [8] with conductive coating for electronic surveillance applications, and printed dipoles [9] etched on a Rogers 3035 substrate with a thickness of 0.762 mm for direction finding applications. In addition to the dipoles and monopoles, there are other antennas that have been developed for use in direction finding applications, such as 3D-printed antennas, corrugated horns, Yagis, and log-periodic antennas.

In this paper, we describe a simulation analysis that explores how the drone body affects the radiation pattern of a printed log-periodic dipole antenna (PLPDA) enclosed in a radome and mounted on the drone with a metallic mast. The proposed PLPDA has dimensions of 230 mm \times 170 mm \times 1 mm and includes 25 dipoles. These dipoles are embedded on an FR4 substrate that is 1mm thick and has a dielectric permittivity equal to 4.3. The PLPDA is mounted on the drone using a mast equal to 106mm in height. In [10], a UAV has been measured in an anechoic chamber and it is observed that the drone body has significant impact on the radiation pattern of the antenna mounted on it. As a result, there was an increase in polarisation mixing, causing degradation of cross-polarization discrimination by 15dB on average.

II. DESIGN

Usually, micro-strip patches, monopoles, and dipoles [11] mounted on drones are developed either with low bandwidth or with low realized gain over the frequency band. However, we require a directional antenna [12] with wide operational bandwidth and flat gain over the band. Such a performance specification calls for a PLPDA with a flat gain of 5.5 dBi [13]. As a structural element, it has some advantages against aerodynamic forces, and its end-fire radiation [14] is a positive aspect. Fig. 1 demonstrates the proposed drone model implemented for experiments. The proposed model is a

customized version of a drone built by Team Hawk at the University of Huddersfield. It has a rotor-to-rotor diagonal length of 405mm, and its mainframe, wings, and arms are made of carbon fibre. Among the main metallic components used in this version, are a bottom plate and four brushless motors. One of the most popular radio telescopes currently in use is the Square Kilometre Array (SKA). The elements of SKA are arranged over a ground metallic mesh at a spacing of approximately two meters. A UAV based on Mikrokopter KGPS ver. 1.0 has been developed to assess the performance of SKA when deployed in a real environment, enabling SKA design to be improved based on the measurements obtained. In [15], an EM model of a Mikrokopter with a dipole has been developed. This electromagnetic model consists of a solid plate that represents a metal grid under the copter arm, two rectangular boxes that represent the frequency generator and transmitter, and a dipole that is connected to the transmitter. Based on a simplified 3D model, [16] investigates and proposes a solution to overcome the effect of RF synthesizers on dipoles. Observations show that metallic components have a significant impact on the dipole performance. According to the above cases, before using drones as a test source it is important to calibrate the mounted antenna for better analysis. In this attempt, to examine the influence of metallic components of drones on the performance of the PLPDA, we perform a simulation analysis.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. (a) Top view, and (b) side view of the quadcopter.

In order to improve the computational efficiency, the simplified quadcopter has been modelled in CST as illustrated in Fig. 2. Four motors with a diameter of 35 mm are positioned at a distance of 145 mm from the quadcopter frame whose dimensions are 250 mm \times 140 mm. As shown in Fig. 2, the EM model consists of a PLPDA mounted at a height of 106 mm from the main structural frame. In this case, the bottom plate is modelled as a single sheet of metal to avoid generating a large number of mesh cells. The EM model is computed with an accuracy of -40 dB and using open boundary conditions. Estimated reflection levels of 0.0001 are used for the simulation, while the minimum separation of the absorbing boundaries to the structure is maintained as $\lambda/4$ at the lowest frequency of operation, i.e., 700 MHz.

Fig. 2. EM model of the quadcopter.

A total of around 75 million hexahedral mesh cells are generated for this simulation with the smallest cell size of 0.08 mm. This structure has been simulated with -40 dB accuracy on a workstation with an Intel(R) Core (TM) i7-5960X Processor @ 3.00GHz (8-core) and 256GB of RAM memory, accelerated by an Nvidia GP100 GPU. Based on these hardware specifications, the simulation took approximately 1 hour to complete. This structure has been simulated by a transient solver, which calculates the development of fields through time at discrete locations and at discrete time samples. The Transient solver is based on the Finite Integration Technique (FIT) which provides a representation of Maxwell's equations in their integral form rather than differential form. With Perfect Boundary Approximation (PBA) [17] and the Thin Sheet Technique (TST) extension, this solver allows the calculation to be performed with better accuracy than other computing techniques utilizing standard hexahedral cells.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we present and discuss the simulation results of the PLPDA placed on a drone platform. Fig. 3 presents a comparison of S11 parameter values produced by PLPDA alone, PLPDA enclosed in a radome mounted on the drone with the assistance of a mast, and PLPDA enclosed in a radome not mounted on the drone but supported by a metallic mast. It is also shown how metallic components such as masts, base plates, and brushless motors shift resonances towards the lower frequency. The PLPDA achieves an operational bandwidth from 0.7 to 6.5 GHz that corresponds to a fractional bandwidth of 160%.

Fig. 3. S11 parameters.

The PLPDA is enclosed in a radome made of PTFE with an electric permittivity of 2.1. Radiation patterns of the PLPDA installed on the drone at 0.8 GHz, 2 GHz, 3 GHz, 7 GHz are depicted in Fig. 4 which compares the polar plots of a PLPDA enclosed in a radome mounted on a drone with metallic mast and a PLPDA alone which is not enclosed in a radome and not mounted on a drone. It is evident that at lower frequencies, i.e., 0.8 and 2 GHz, the radiation pattern gets distorted due to the grounding effect caused by the metallic base plate and brushless motors.

Fig. 4. Radiation patterns in the elevation plane at (a) 0.8 GHz, (b) 2 GHz, (c) 3 GHz, and (d) 7 GHz.

Table I. shows the comparison between the half-power beamwidth of PLPDA enclosed in a radome mounted on a drone with a metallic mast and the half-power beamwidth of PLPDA by itself without enclosure at 0.8, 2, 3 and 7 GHz. It is observed that at 0.8, 2, and 3 GHz, the beam gets narrowed by 3° on an average. On the other hand, at 7 GHz, the beam widens by 2° .

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF HALF POWER BEAMWIDTH

Frequency (GHz)	HPBW for PLPDA with drone	HPBW for PLPDA alone
0.8	67°	70°
2	60°	63°
3	59°	62°
7	64°	62°

In Fig. 5, a comparison is provided in terms of realized gain among the entire structure using a PLPDA with a metallic mast mounted on a drone, a PLPDA with mast and a PLPDA alone.

Fig. 5. Simulation results of realized gain.

It is observed that the metallic mast used to mount the antenna has a significant impact on current distribution. It acts like a reflector channelling the energy towards the boresight. From Fig. 5, it is evident that the realized gain is improved by 1.3 dB on average from 2 to 6.5 GHz due to the mast. Metal components on drone provide another 0.3 dB improvement in realized gain over this frequency range.

IV. STATE OF ART

With the development of UAV technology and miniaturization of RF components such as portable network analyzer, UAV carrying a probe is a preferred solution to calibrate the antenna deployed in field. Before calibrating the system, it is essential to make sure that test source is working as per the design specifications without any degradation due to the UAV body. In [18] dual-polarized quad-ridge horn operating in 3 to 32 GHz is mounted on DJI Matrices 600P UAV. To understand the effect of drone body on the radiation pattern of antenna, UAV carrying the horn is measured in indoor far-field anechoic chamber. To eliminate the variables and to understand the influence of drone body, same dual-

polarized quad ridge horn is used as probe in the anechoic chamber. By comparing the measured results of horn which is not mounted on UAV with measured data of horn mounted on UAV it is observed that due to the metallic components on the UAV there is degradation in cross-polarization levels by 7 dB for frequencies below 10 GHz and at higher frequencies above 10 GHz degradation in the cross-polarization levels are less than 4 dB. In [19] a conformal high-order mode circular patch antenna (HMCPA) with TM_{21} resonance mode and operating at 700 MHz is proposed for UAV application. Since the proposed antenna is conformal it can be easily integrated to the UAV body. HMCPA is mounted at the bottom of UAV fuselage. Complete UAV structure with antenna is simulated and analyzing the simulation results it is observed that when HMCPA is integrated with UAV there is a resonance shift towards lower frequency. Presence of metallic components such as batteries, RF synthesizer, motors and base plate of UAV scatters the electromagnetic waves (EM) which results in the degradation of RF performance of antenna. To overcome these effects in [20] 3×3 S-Band array is designed to have narrow beamwidth to minimize the reflections from UAV body. Proposed design has been validated in anechoic chamber and it is noticed that it had minimum distortions in cross-polarizations levels.

With a growing demand for different kind of antenna to be mounted on UAV researchers have proposed alternative to commonly used micro-strip patch antenna. In [21] a quasi-yagi antenna array operating at 24GHz with an end-fire radiation pattern is designed. A linear array of 4 elements with corporate feeding is used to achieve a gain of 13.6 dBi and HPBW of 16. Proposed model can be easily integrated on the UAV body without much distortions in its RF performance. Similarly blade antenna (Planar Monopole resonators) are widely used to integrate in UAV. In [22] analysis of blade antenna on Mavic pro and DJI phantom 3 are considered. Blade antenna is designed to resonate at 1.09 GHz and with a resonant cavity a second resonance is achieved at 3.5 GHz for 5G application. All the simulations are performed in CST Studio Suite with motors and ground plate of the UAV as PEC and UAV body as polyactic acid (plastic composite polymer) with relative permittivity ($\epsilon_r = 2.62$) and loss tangent ($\tan \delta = 0.014$). After the UAV carrying the blade antenna is simulated it is observed that in case of Mavic pro resonance shifts by 100 MHz towards lower frequency due to the ground plate at the bottom and for Phantom 3 with smaller ground plate resonance shifts by 50 MHz towards higher frequency.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a simulation has been implemented to assess the performance of a wideband antenna installed on drones. The PLPDA has an advantage in terms of end-fire radiation patterns and structural strength against aerodynamic forces. A study has been performed to determine the effects of metallic components on the antenna system. Due to the metallic components of the drone, we have observed that at lower frequencies up to 2 GHz the radiation pattern is degraded. Based on the simulation results, it is evident that there is an

improvement of 1.6 dB in the realized gain in the frequency range from 2 to 6.5 GHz, of which 1.3 dB is due to the mast and 0.3 dB is due to the quadcopter baseplate. Pattern distortions observed at the frequencies below 2 GHz can be minimized by finding the optimum position and orientation of the PLPDA mounted on drone.

VI. FUTURE WORK

The above-described work is a study that quantifies the performance of PLPDA mounted on a UAV. The scope of work for this project is extensive, as it involves simulations in combination with measurements in anechoic chambers. This work involves including more details to the UAV structure, such as power supplies (batteries) and GPS sensors which is essential to the drone's accuracy in terms of its position. Such components can be potential scatterers of EM waves. Optimization and in-depth analysis are required to estimate the optimum location for these components and antenna to avoid the RF performance degradation, which is essential before using a UAV carrying the probe as a far-field source to measure systems deployed in the field.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was supported by the European Union through the Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Networks Programme "Mobility and Training for beyond 5G Ecosystems (MOTOR5G)" under grant agreement no. 861219.

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